

Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection On Pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifolds

C.Patra

(Govt.Degree College, Kamalpur, Dhalai, Tripura, India)

A.Bhattacharyya

(Department of Mathematics, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700032, India)

E-mail: patrachinmoy@yahoo.co.in, aribh22@hotmail.com

Abstract: The object of this paper is to introduce a quarter-symmetric metric connection in a pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold and to study of some properties of it. Also we shall discuss some properties of the Weyl-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold and Ricci-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. We have given an example of pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection.

Key Words: Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold, quarter-symmetric metric connection, pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds, Ricci-pseudosymmetric, Weyl-pseudosymmetric, η -Einstein manifold.

AMS(2010): 53B30, 53C15, 53C25

§1. Introduction

The theory of pseudosymmetric manifold has been developed by many authors by two ways. One is the Chaki sense [8], [3] and another is Deszcz sense [2], [9], [11]. In this paper we shall study some properties of pseudosymmetric and Ricci-symmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection in Deszcz sense. The notion of pseudo-symmetry is a natural generalization of semi-symmetry, along the line of spaces of constant sectional curvature and locally symmetric space.

A Riemannian manifold (M, g) of dimension n is said to be pseudosymmetric if the Riemannian curvature tensor R satisfies the conditions ([1]):

$$1. (R(X, Y).R)(U, V, W) = L_R[(X \wedge Y).R)(U, V, W)] \quad (1)$$

for all vector fields X, Y, U, V, W on M , where $L_R \in C^\infty(M)$, $R(X, Y)Z = \nabla_{[X, Y]}Z - [\nabla_X, \nabla_Y]Z$ and $X \wedge Y$ is an endomorphism defined by

$$(X \wedge Y)Z = g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y \quad (2)$$

¹Received October 6, 2012. Accepted March 6, 2013.

$$2. (R(X, Y).R)(U, V, W) = R(X, Y)(R(U, V)W) - R(R(X, Y)U, V)W \\ - R(U, R(X, Y)V)W - R(U, V)(R(X, Y)W) \quad (3)$$

$$3. ((X \wedge Y).R)(U, V, W) = (X \wedge Y)(R(U, V)W) - R((X \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ - R(U, (X \wedge Y)V)W - R(U, V)((X \wedge Y)W). \quad (4)$$

M is said to be pseudosymmetric of constant type if L is constant. A Riemannian manifold (M, g) is called semi-symmetric if $R.R = 0$, where $R.R$ is the derivative of R by R .

Remark 1.1 We know, the $(0, k+2)$ tensor fields $R.T$ and $Q(g, T)$ are defined by

$$(R.T)(X_1, \dots, X_k; X, Y) = (R(X, Y).T)(X_1, \dots, X_k) \\ = -T(R(X, Y)X_1, \dots, X_k) - \dots - T(X_1, \dots, R(X, Y)X_k) \\ Q(g, T)(X_1, \dots, X_k; X, Y) = -((X \wedge Y).T)(X_1, \dots, X_k) \\ = T((X \wedge Y)X_1, \dots, X_k) + \dots + T(X_1, \dots, (X \wedge Y)X_k),$$

where T is a $(0, k)$ tensor field ([4],[5]).

Let S and r denote the Ricci tensor and the scalar curvature tensor of M respectively. The operator Q and the $(0, 2)$ -tensor S^2 are defined by

$$S(X, Y) = g(QX, Y) \quad (5)$$

and

$$S^2(X, Y) = S(QX, Y) \quad (6)$$

The Weyl conformal curvature operator C is defined by

$$C(X, Y) = R(X, Y) - \frac{1}{n-2}[X \wedge QY + QX \wedge Y - \frac{r}{n-1}X \wedge Y]. \quad (7)$$

If $C = 0$, $n \geq 3$ then M is called conformally flat. If the tensor $R.C$ and $Q(g, C)$ are linearly dependent then M is called Weyl-pseudosymmetric. This is equivalent to

$$R.C(U, V, W; X, Y) = L_C[((X \wedge Y).C)(U, V)W], \quad (8)$$

holds on the set $U_C = \{x \in M : C \neq 0 \text{ at } x\}$, where L_C is defined on U_C . If $R.C = 0$, then M is called Weyl-semi-symmetric. If $\nabla C = 0$, then M is called conformally symmetric ([6],[10]).

§2. Preliminaries

A n -dimensional differentiable manifold M is said to be a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold if it admits a $(1, 1)$ -tensor field ϕ , a contravariant vector field ξ , a covariant vector field η and Lorentzian metric g which satisfy the following conditions,

$$\phi^2 = I + \eta \otimes \xi, \quad (9)$$

$$\eta(\xi) = -1, \quad \phi\xi = 0, \quad \eta \circ \phi = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y), \quad (11)$$

$$g(X, \xi) = \eta(X) \quad (12)$$

and

$$(\nabla_X \phi)(Y) = \alpha\{g(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X\} \quad (13)$$

for $\forall X, Y \in \chi(M)$ and for smooth functions α on M , ∇ denotes covariant differentiation operator with respect to Lorentzian metric g ([6], [7]).

For a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold, it can be shown that ([6],[7]):

$$\nabla_X \xi = \alpha\phi X, \quad (14)$$

$$(\nabla_X \eta)Y = \alpha g(\phi X, Y). \quad (15)$$

Further on a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold, the following relations hold ([6])

$$\eta(R(X, Y)Z) = \alpha^2[g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)], \quad (16)$$

$$R(\xi, X)Y = \alpha^2[g(Y, Z)\xi - \eta(Y)X], \quad (17)$$

$$R(X, Y)\xi = \alpha^2[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y], \quad (18)$$

$$S(\xi, X) = S(X, \xi) = (n-1)\alpha^2\eta(X), \quad (19)$$

$$S(\xi, \xi) = -(n-1)\alpha^2, \quad (20)$$

$$Q\xi = (n-1)\alpha^2\xi. \quad (21)$$

The above relations will be used in following sections.

§3. Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection on Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold

Let M be a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with Levi-Civita connection ∇ and $X, Y, Z \in \chi(M)$. We define a linear connection D on M by

$$D_X Y = \nabla_X Y + \eta(Y)\phi(X) \quad (22)$$

where η is 1-form and ϕ is a tensor field of type $(1, 1)$. D is said to be quarter-symmetric connection if \bar{T} , the torsion tensor with respect to the connection D , satisfies

$$\bar{T}(X, Y) = \eta(Y)\phi X - \eta(X)\phi Y. \quad (23)$$

D is said to be metric connection if

$$(D_X g)(Y, Z) = 0. \quad (24)$$

A linear connection D is said to be quarter-symmetric metric connection if it satisfies (22), (23) and (24).

Now we shall show the existence of the quarter-symmetric metric connection D on a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M .

Theorem 3.1 *Let X, Y, Z be any vectors fields on a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M and let a connection D is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} 2g(D_X Y, Z) &= Xg(Y, Z) + Yg(Z, X) - Zg(X, Y) + g([X, Y], Z) \\ &\quad - g([Y, Z], X) + g([Z, X], Y) + g(\eta(Y)\phi X - \eta(X)\phi Y, Z) \\ &\quad + g(\eta(X)\phi Z - \eta(Z)\phi X, Y) + g(\eta(Y)\phi Z - \eta(Z)\phi Y, X). \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Then D is a quarter-symmetric metric connection on M .

Proof It can be verified that $D : (X, Y) \rightarrow D_X Y$ satisfies the following equations:

$$D_X(Y + Z) = D_X Y + D_X Z, \quad (26)$$

$$D_{X+Y} Z = D_X Z + D_Y Z, \quad (27)$$

$$D_{fX} Y = fD_X Y, \quad (28)$$

$$D_X(fY) = f(D_X Y) + (Xf)Y \quad (29)$$

for all $X, Y, Z \in \chi(M)$ and for all f , differentiable function on M .

From (26), (27), (28) and (29), we can conclude that D is a linear connection on M . From (25) we have,

$$g(D_X Y, Z) - g(D_Y X, Z) = g([X, Y], Z) + \eta(Y)g(\phi X, Z) - \eta(X)g(\phi Y, Z)$$

or,

$$D_X Y - D_Y X - [X, Y] = \eta(Y)\phi X - \eta(X)\phi Y$$

or,

$$\bar{T}(X, Y) = \eta(Y)\phi X - \eta(X)\phi Y \quad (30)$$

Again from (25) we get,

$$2g(D_X Y, Z) + 2g(D_X Z, Y) = 2Xg(Y, Z), \quad \text{or,} \quad (D_X g)(Y, Z) = 0.$$

This shows that D is a quarter-symmetric metric connection on M . \square

§4. Curvature Tensor and Ricci Tensor with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection D in a Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold

Let $\bar{R}(X, Y)Z$ and $R(X, Y)Z$ be the curvature tensors with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D and with respect to the Riemannian connection ∇ respectively on a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M . A relation between the curvature tensors $\bar{R}(X, Y)Z$ and $R(X, Y)Z$ on M is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + \alpha[g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y \\ &\quad - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X] + \alpha\eta(Z)[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y]. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Also from (31), we obtain

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = S(X, Y) + \alpha[g(X, Y) + n\eta(X)\eta(Y)], \quad (32)$$

where \bar{S} and S are the Ricci tensors of the connections D and ∇ respectively.

Again

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{S}^2(X, Y) &= S^2(X, Y) - \alpha(n-2)S(X, Y) - \alpha^2(n-1)g(X, Y) \\ &\quad + \alpha^2 n(n-1)(\alpha-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y).\end{aligned}\tag{33}$$

Contracting (32), we get

$$\bar{r} = r,\tag{34}$$

where \bar{r} and r are the scalar curvature with respect to the connection D and ∇ respectively.

Let \bar{C} be the conformal curvature tensors on Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds with respect to the connections D . Then

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{C}(X, Y)Z &= \bar{R}(X, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-2}[\bar{S}(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)\bar{Q}Y + g(Y, Z)\bar{Q}X \\ &\quad - \bar{S}(X, Z)Y] + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y],\end{aligned}\tag{35}$$

where \bar{Q} is Ricci operator with the connection D on M and

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = g(\bar{Q}X, Y),\tag{36}$$

$$\bar{S}^2(X, Y) = \bar{S}(\bar{Q}X, Y).\tag{37}$$

Now we shall prove the following theorem.

Theorem 4.1 *Let M be a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D , then the following relations hold:*

$$\bar{R}(\xi, X)Y = \alpha^2[g(X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)X] + \alpha\eta(Y)[X + \eta(X)\xi],\tag{38}$$

$$\eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z) = \alpha^2[g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)],\tag{39}$$

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi = (\alpha^2 - \alpha)[\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y],\tag{40}$$

$$\bar{S}(X, \xi) = \bar{S}(\xi, X) = (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\eta(X),\tag{41}$$

$$\bar{S}^2(X, \xi) = \bar{S}^2(\xi, X) = \alpha^2(n-1)^2(\alpha-1)^2\eta(X),\tag{42}$$

$$\bar{S}(\xi, \xi) = -(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha),\tag{43}$$

$$\bar{Q}X = QX - \alpha(n-1)X,\tag{44}$$

$$\bar{Q}\xi = (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\xi.\tag{45}$$

Proof Since M is a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D , then replacing $X = \xi$ in (31) and using (10) and (17) we get (38). Using (10) and (16), from (31) we get (39). To prove (40), we put $Z = \xi$ in (31) and then we use (18). Replacing $Y = \xi$ in (32) and using (19) we get (41). Putting $Y = \xi$ in (33) and using (6) and (19) we get (42). Again putting $X = Y = \xi$ in (32) and using (20) we get (43). Using (36) and (41) we get (44). Then putting $X = \xi$ in (44) we get (45). \square

§5. Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold with Respect to the Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection D Satisfying the Condition $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$.

In this section we shall find out the characterization of Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D satisfying the condition $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$. We define $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$ on M by

$$(\bar{C}(X, Y).\bar{S})(Z, W) = -\bar{S}(\bar{C}(X, Y)Z, W) - \bar{S}(Z, \bar{C}(X, Y)W), \quad (46)$$

where $X, Y, Z, W \in \chi(M)$.

Theorem 5.1 *Let M be an n -dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D . If $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n-2}\bar{S}^2(X, Y) &= [(\alpha^2 - \alpha) + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}]\bar{S}(X, Y) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha^2 - \alpha}{n-2}[\alpha(n-1)(\alpha - n + 1) - \bar{r}]g(X, Y) \\ &- \alpha(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\eta(X)\eta(Y). \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Proof Let us consider M be an n -dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect the quarter-symmetric metric connection D satisfying the condition $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$. Then from (46), we get

$$\bar{S}(\bar{C}(X, Y)Z, W) + \bar{S}(Z, \bar{C}(X, Y)W) = 0, \quad (48)$$

where $X, Y, Z, W \in \chi(M)$. Now putting $X = \xi$ in (48), we get

$$\bar{S}(\bar{C}(\xi, X)Y, Z) + \bar{S}(Y, \bar{C}(\xi, X)Z) = 0. \quad (49)$$

Using (35), (37), (38) and (41), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}(\bar{C}(\xi, X)Y, Z) &= (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)[\alpha^2 - \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}]\eta(Z)g(X, Y) \\ &+ [\alpha - \alpha^2 + \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} - \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}]\eta(Y)\bar{S}(X, Z) \\ &+ \alpha(\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) \\ &- \frac{1}{n-2}[(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\eta(Z)\bar{S}(X, Y) - \bar{S}^2(X, Z)\eta(Y)] \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}(Y, \bar{C}(\xi, X)Z) &= (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)[\alpha^2 - \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}]\eta(Y)g(X, Z) \\ &+ [\alpha - \alpha^2 + \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} - \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)}]\eta(Z)\bar{S}(Y, X) \\ &+ \alpha(\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) \\ &- \frac{1}{n-2}[(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\eta(Y)\bar{S}(X, Z) - \bar{S}^2(X, Y)\eta(Z)]. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Using (50) and (51) in (49), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha) \left[\alpha^2 - \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)} \right] [g(X, Y)\eta(Z) \\
& + g(X, Z)\eta(Y)] + 2\alpha(\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) \\
& + \left[\alpha - \alpha^2 + \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} - \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)} \right] [\eta(Y)\bar{S}(X, Z) + \eta(Z)\bar{S}(Y, X)] \\
& - \frac{1}{n-2} [(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\{\eta(Z)\bar{S}(X, Y) + \eta(Y)\bar{S}(X, Z)\} \\
& - \{\bar{S}^2(X, Z)\eta(Y) + \bar{S}^2(X, Y)\eta(Z)\}] = 0. \tag{52}
\end{aligned}$$

Replacing $Z = \xi$ in (52) and using (41) and (42), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{n-2}\bar{S}^2(X, Y) &= \left[(\alpha^2 - \alpha) + \frac{\bar{r}}{(n-1)(n-2)} \right] \bar{S}(X, Y) \\
&+ \frac{\alpha^2 - \alpha}{n-2} [\alpha(n-1)(\alpha - n + 1) - \bar{r}]g(X, Y) \\
&- \alpha(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\eta(X)\eta(Y). \quad \square
\end{aligned}$$

An n -dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with the quarter-symmetric metric connection D is said to be η -Einstein if its Ricci tensor \bar{S} is of the form

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = Ag(X, Y) + B\eta(X)\eta(Y), \tag{53}$$

where A, B are smooth functions of M . Now putting $X = Y = e_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ in (53) and taking summation for $1 \leq i \leq n$ we get

$$An - B = \bar{r}. \tag{54}$$

Again replacing $X = Y = \xi$ in (53) we have

$$A - B = (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha). \tag{55}$$

Solving (54) and (55) we obtain

$$A = \frac{\bar{r}}{n-1} - (\alpha^2 - \alpha) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \frac{\bar{r}}{n-1} - n(\alpha^2 - \alpha).$$

Thus the Ricci tensor of an η -Einstein manifold with the quarter-symmetric metric connection D is given by

$$\bar{S}(X, Y) = \left[\frac{\bar{r}}{n-1} - (\alpha^2 - \alpha) \right] g(X, Y) + \left[\frac{\bar{r}}{n-1} - n(\alpha^2 - \alpha) \right] \eta(X)\eta(Y). \tag{56}$$

§6. η -Einstein Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold with Respect to the Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection D Satisfying the Condition $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$.

Theorem 6.1 *Let M be an η -Einstein Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold of dimension. Then $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$ iff*

$$\frac{n\alpha - 2\alpha}{n\alpha^2 - 2\alpha} [\eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z)\eta(W) + \eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)W)\eta(Z)] = 0,$$

where $X, Y, Z, W \in \chi(M)$.

Proof Let M be an η -Einstein Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection D satisfying $\bar{C}.\bar{S} = 0$. Using (56) in (48), we get

$$\eta(\bar{C}(X, Y)Z)\eta(W) + \eta(\bar{C}(X, Y)W)\eta(Z) = 0,$$

or,

$$\frac{n\alpha - 2\alpha}{n\alpha^2 - 2\alpha}[\eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z)\eta(W) + \eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)W)\eta(Z)] = 0.$$

Conversely, using (56) we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{C}(X, Y).\bar{S})(Z, W) &= -\left[\frac{\bar{r}}{n-1} - n(\alpha^2 - \alpha)\right][\eta(\bar{C}(X, Y)Z)\eta(W) + \eta(\bar{C}(X, Y)W)\eta(Z)] \\ &= -\frac{n\alpha - 2\alpha}{n\alpha^2 - 2\alpha}[\eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z)\eta(W) + \eta(\bar{R}(X, Y)W)\eta(Z)] = 0. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

§7. Ricci Pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifolds with Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection D

Theorem 7.1 *A Ricci pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with quarter-symmetric metric connection D with restriction $Y = W = \xi$ and $L_{\bar{S}} = 1$ is an η -Einstein manifold.*

Proof Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with quarter-symmetric metric connection D is called a Ricci pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold if

$$(\bar{R}(X, Y).\bar{S})(Z, W) = L_{\bar{S}}[(X \wedge Y).\bar{S})(Z, W)], \quad (57)$$

or,

$$\bar{S}(\bar{R}(X, Y)Z, W) + \bar{S}(Z, \bar{R}(X, Y)W) = L_{\bar{S}}[\bar{S}((X \wedge Y)Z, W) + \bar{S}(Z, (X \wedge Y)W)]. \quad (58)$$

Putting $Y = W = \xi$ in (58) and using (2), (38) and (41), we have

$$\begin{aligned} &L_{\bar{S}}[\bar{S}(X, Z) - (n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)g(X, Z)] \\ &= (\alpha^2 - \alpha)\bar{S}(X, Z) - \alpha^2(\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)g(X, Z) - \alpha(\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Z). \quad (59) \end{aligned}$$

Then for $L_{\bar{S}} = 1$,

$$(\alpha^2 - \alpha - 1)\bar{S}(X, Z) = (\alpha^2 - \alpha)(n-1)[(\alpha^2 - 1)g(X, Z) + \alpha\eta(X)\eta(Z)].$$

Thus M is an η -Einstein manifold. □

Corollary 7.1 *A Ricci semisymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with quarter-symmetric metric connection D with restriction $Y = W = \xi$ is an η -Einstein manifold.*

Proof Since M is Ricci semisymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds with quarter-symmetric metric connection D , then $L_{\bar{C}} = 0$. Putting $L_{\bar{C}} = 0$ in (59) we get

$$\bar{S}(X, Z) = \alpha^2(n-1)g(X, Z) + \alpha(n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Z). \quad \square$$

§8. Pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold and Weyl-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian Manifold with Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

In the present section we shall give the definition of pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold and Weyl-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection and discuss some properties on it.

Definition 8.1 A Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with quarter-symmetric metric connection D is said to be pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection if the curvature tensor \bar{R} of M with respect to D satisfies the conditions

$$(\bar{R}(X, Y).\bar{R})(U, V, W) = L_{\bar{R}}[(X \wedge Y).\bar{R})(U, V, W)], \quad (60)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{R}(X, Y).\bar{R})(U, V, W) &= \bar{R}(X, Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}(\bar{R}(X, Y)U, V)W \\ &\quad - \bar{R}(U, \bar{R}(X, Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)(R(X, Y)W), \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} ((X \wedge Y).\bar{R})(U, V, W) &= (X \wedge Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}((X \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ &\quad - \bar{R}(U, (X \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)((X \wedge Y)W). \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

Definition 8.2 A Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold M with quarter-symmetric metric connection D is said to be Weyl-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection if the curvature tensor \bar{R} of M with respect to D satisfies the conditions

$$(\bar{R}(X, Y).\bar{C})(U, V, W) = L_{\bar{C}}[(X \wedge Y).\bar{C})(U, V, W)], \quad (63)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{R}(X, Y).\bar{C})(U, V, W) &= \bar{R}(X, Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}(\bar{R}(X, Y)U, V)W \\ &\quad - \bar{C}(U, \bar{R}(X, Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)(R(X, Y)W) \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} ((X \wedge Y).\bar{C})(U, V, W) &= (X \wedge Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}((X \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ &\quad - \bar{C}(U, (X \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)((X \wedge Y)W). \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Theorem 8.1 Let M be an n dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold. If M is Weyl-pseudosymmetric then M is either conformally flat and M is η -Einstein manifold or $L_{\bar{C}} = \alpha^2$.

Proof Let M be an Weyl-pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold and $X, Y, U, V, W \in \chi(M)$. Then using (64) and (65) in (63), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{R}(X, Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}(\bar{R}(X, Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{C}(U, \bar{R}(X, Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)(R(X, Y)W) \\ & = L_{\bar{C}}[(X \wedge Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}((X \wedge Y)U, V)W] \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

$$- \bar{C}(U, (X \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)((X \wedge Y)W)]. \quad (67)$$

Replacing X with ξ in (66) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{R}(\xi, Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}(\bar{R}(\xi, Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{C}(U, \bar{R}(\xi, Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)(R(\xi, Y)W) \\ & = L_{\bar{C}}[(\xi \wedge Y)(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - \bar{C}((\xi \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{C}(U, (\xi \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{C}(U, V)((\xi \wedge Y)W)]. \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

Using (2), (38) in (67) and taking inner product of (67) with ξ , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha^2[-\bar{C}(U, V, W, Y) - \eta(\bar{C}(U, V)W)\eta(Y) - g(Y, U)\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) \\ & + \eta(U)\eta(\bar{C}(Y, V)W) - g(Y, V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, \xi)W) + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, Y)W) \\ & + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{C}(U, V)Y)] - \alpha[\eta(U)\eta(\bar{C}(\phi^2 Y, V)W) \\ & + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, \phi^2 Y)W) + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{C}(U, V)\phi^2 Y)] \\ & = L_{\bar{C}}[-\bar{C}(Y, U, V, W) - \eta(Y)\eta(\bar{C}(U, V)W) - g(Y, U)\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) \\ & + \eta(U)\eta(\bar{C}(Y, V)W) - g(Y, V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, \xi)W) + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, Y)W) \\ & + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{C}(U, V)Y)]. \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

Putting $Y = U$, we get

$$[L_{\bar{C}} - \alpha^2][g(U, U)\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) + g(U, V)\eta(\bar{C}(U, \xi)W)] + \alpha\eta(V)\eta(\bar{C}(\phi^2 U, V)W) = 0. \quad (70)$$

Replacing $U = \xi$ in (68), we obtain

$$[L_{\bar{C}} - \alpha^2]\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) = 0. \quad (71)$$

The formula (69) gives either $\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) = 0$ or $L_{\bar{C}} - \alpha^2 = 0$.

Now $L_{\bar{C}} - \alpha^2 \neq 0$, then $\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) = 0$, then we have M is conformally flat and which gives

$$\bar{S}(V, W) = Ag(V, W) + B\eta(V)\eta(W),$$

where

$$A = [\alpha^2 - \frac{(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} + \frac{r}{(n-1)(n-2)}](n-2)$$

and

$$B = [\alpha^2 - \frac{2(n-1)(\alpha^2 - \alpha)}{n-2} + \frac{r}{(n-1)(n-2)}](n-2),$$

which shows that M is an η -Einstein manifold. Now if $\eta(\bar{C}(\xi, V)W) \neq 0$, then $L_{\bar{C}} = \alpha^2$. \square

Theorem 8.2 *Let M be an n dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold. If M is pseudosymmetric then either M is a space of constant curvature and $\alpha g(X, Y) = \eta(X)\eta(Y)$, for $\alpha \neq 0$ or $L_{\bar{R}} = \alpha^2$, for $X, Y \in \chi(M)$.*

Proof Let M be a pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold and $X, Y, U, V, W \in \chi(M)$. Then using (61) and (62) in (60), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{R}(X, Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}(\bar{R}(X, Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{R}(U, \bar{R}(X, Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)(R(X, Y)W) \\ & = L_{\bar{R}}[(X \wedge Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}((X \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{R}(U, (X \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)((X \wedge Y)W)]. \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

Replacing X with ξ in (70) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{R}(\xi, Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}(\bar{R}(\xi, Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{R}(U, \bar{R}(\xi, Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)(R(\xi, Y)W) \\ & = L_{\bar{R}}[(\xi \wedge Y)(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - \bar{R}((\xi \wedge Y)U, V)W \\ & - \bar{R}(U, (\xi \wedge Y)V)W - \bar{R}(U, V)((\xi \wedge Y)W)]. \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

Using (2), (38) in (71) and taking inner product of (71) with ξ , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha^2[-\bar{R}(U, V, W, Y) - \eta(\bar{R}(U, V)W)\eta(Y) - g(Y, U)\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) \\ & + \eta(U)\eta(\bar{R}(Y, V)W) - g(Y, V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, \xi)W) + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, Y)W) \\ & + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{R}(U, V)Y)] - \alpha[\eta(U)\eta(\bar{R}(\phi^2 Y, V)W) \\ & + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, \phi^2 Y)W) + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{R}(U, V)\phi^2 Y)] \\ & = L_{\bar{R}}[-\bar{R}(Y, U, V, W) - \eta(Y)\eta(\bar{R}(U, V)W) - g(Y, U)\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) \\ & + \eta(U)\eta(\bar{R}(Y, V)W) - g(Y, V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, \xi)W) + \eta(V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, Y)W) \\ & + \eta(W)\eta(\bar{R}(U, V)Y)]. \end{aligned}$$

Putting $Y = U$, we get

$$[L_{\bar{R}} - \alpha^2][g(U, U)\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) + g(U, V)\eta(\bar{R}(U, \xi)W)] + \alpha\eta(V)\eta(\bar{R}(\phi^2 U, V)W) = 0. \quad (74)$$

Replacing $U = \xi$ in (72), we obtain

$$[L_{\bar{R}} - \alpha^2]\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) = 0. \quad (75)$$

The formula (73) gives either $\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) = 0$ or $L_{\bar{R}} - \alpha^2 = 0$. Now $L_{\bar{R}} - \alpha^2 \neq 0$, then $\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) = 0$. We have M is a space of constant curvature and $\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) = 0$ gives $\alpha g(V, W) = \eta(X)\eta(Y)$ for $\alpha \neq 0$. If $\eta(\bar{R}(\xi, V)W) \neq 0$, then we have $L_{\bar{R}} = \alpha^2$. \square

§9. Examples

Let us consider the three dimensional manifold $M = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3) \in R^3 : x_1, x_2, x_3 \in R\}$, where (x_1, x_2, x_3) are the standard coordinates of R^3 . We consider the vector fields

$$e_1 = e^{x_3} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}, \quad e_2 = e^{x_3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad e_3 = \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3},$$

where α is a constant.

Clearly, $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is a set of linearly independent vectors for each point of M and hence a basis of $\chi(M)$. The Lorentzian metric g is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} g(e_1, e_2) &= g(e_2, e_3) = g(e_1, e_3) = 0, \\ g(e_1, e_1) &= g(e_2, e_2) = g(e_3, e_3) = -1. \end{aligned}$$

Then the form of metric becomes

$$g = \frac{1}{(e^{x_3})^2} (dx_2)^2 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2} (dx_3)^2,$$

which is a Lorentzian metric.

Let η be the 1-form defined by $\eta(Z) = g(Z, e_3)$ for any $Z \in \chi(M)$ and the $(1, 1)$ -tensor field ϕ is defined by

$$\phi e_1 = -e_1, \quad \phi e_2 = -e_2, \quad \phi e_3 = 0.$$

From the linearity of ϕ and g , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(e_3) &= -1, \\ \phi^2(X) &= X + \eta(X)e_3 \quad \text{and} \\ g(\phi X, \phi Y) &= g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y) \end{aligned}$$

for any $X \in \chi(M)$. Then for $e_3 = \xi$, the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) defines a Lorentzian paracontact structure on M .

Let ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection with respect to the Lorentzian metric g . Then we have

$$[e_1, e_2] = 0, \quad [e_1, e_3] = -\alpha e_1, \quad [e_2, e_3] = -\alpha e_2.$$

Koszul's formula is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} 2g(\nabla_X Y, Z) &= Xg(Y, Z) + Yg(Z, X) - Zg(X, Y) \\ &\quad - g(X, [Y, Z]) - g(Y, [X, Z]) + g(Z, [X, Y]). \end{aligned}$$

Then from above formula we can calculate the followings,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{e_1} e_1 &= -\alpha e_3, \quad \nabla_{e_1} e_2 = 0, \quad \nabla_{e_1} e_3 = -\alpha e_1, \\ \nabla_{e_2} e_1 &= 0, \quad \nabla_{e_2} e_2 = -\alpha e_3, \quad \nabla_{e_2} e_3 = -\alpha e_2, \\ \nabla_{e_3} e_1 &= 0, \quad \nabla_{e_3} e_2 = 0, \quad \nabla_{e_3} e_3 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) is a Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold [7].

Using (22), we find D , the quarter-symmetric metric connection on M following:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{e_1} e_1 &= -\alpha e_3, \quad D_{e_1} e_2 = 0, \quad D_{e_1} e_3 = e_1(1 - \alpha), \\ D_{e_2} e_1 &= 0, \quad D_{e_2} e_2 = -\alpha e_3, \quad D_{e_2} e_3 = e_2(1 - \alpha), \\ D_{e_3} e_1 &= 0, \quad D_{e_3} e_2 = 0, \quad D_{e_3} e_3 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Using (23), the torsion tensor \bar{T} , with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection D as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{T}(e_i, e_i) &= 0, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, 3 \\ \bar{T}(e_1, e_2) &= 0, \quad \bar{T}(e_1, e_3) = e_1, \quad \bar{T}(e_2, e_3) = e_2.\end{aligned}$$

Also $(D_{e_1}g)(e_2, e_3) = (D_{e_2}g)(e_3, e_1) = (D_{e_3}g)(e_1, e_2) = 0$. Thus M is Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection D .

Now we calculate curvature tensor \bar{R} and Ricci tensors \bar{S} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{R}(e_1, e_2)e_3 &= 0, \quad \bar{R}(e_1, e_3)e_3 = -(\alpha^2 - \alpha)e_1, \\ \bar{R}(e_3, e_2)e_2 &= \alpha^2 e_3, \quad \bar{R}(e_3, e_1)e_1 = \alpha^2 e_3, \\ \bar{R}(e_2, e_1)e_1 &= (\alpha^2 - \alpha)e_2, \quad \bar{R}(e_2, e_3)e_3 = -\alpha^2 e_2, \\ \bar{R}(e_1, e_2)e_2 &= (\alpha^2 - \alpha)e_1. \\ \bar{S}(e_1, e_1) &= \bar{S}(e_2, e_2) = -\alpha \text{ and } \bar{S}(e_3, e_3) = -2\alpha^2 + (n-1)\alpha.\end{aligned}$$

Again using (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned}(e_1, e_2)e_3 &= 0, \quad (e_i \wedge e_i)e_j = 0, \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, 3, \\ (e_1 \wedge e_2)e_2 &= (e_1 \wedge e_3)e_3 = -e_1, \quad (e_2 \wedge e_1)e_1 = (e_2 \wedge e_3)e_3 = -e_2, \\ (e_3 \wedge e_2)e_2 &= (e_3 \wedge e_1)e_1 = -e_3.\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{R}(e_1, e_2)(\bar{R}(e_3, e_1)e_2) &= 0, \quad \bar{R}(\bar{R}(e_1, e_2)e_3, e_1)e_2 = 0, \\ \bar{R}(e_3, \bar{R}(e_1, e_2)e_1)e_2 &= -\alpha^2(\alpha^2 - \alpha)e_3, \\ (\bar{R}(e_3, e_1)(\bar{R}(e_1, e_2)e_2)) &= \alpha^2(\alpha^2 - \alpha)e_3.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(\bar{R}(e_1, e_2).\bar{R})(e_3, e_1, e_2) = 0$.

Again,

$$\begin{aligned}(e_1 \wedge e_2)(\bar{R}(e_3, e_1)e_2) &= 0, \quad \bar{R}((e_1 \wedge e_2)e_3, e_1)e_2 = 0, \\ \bar{R}(e_3, (e_1 \wedge e_2)e_1)e_2 &= \alpha^2 e_3, \quad \bar{R}(e_3, e_1)((e_1 \wedge e_2)e_2) = -\alpha^2 e_3.\end{aligned}$$

Then $((e_1, e_2).\bar{R})(e_3, e_1, e_2) = 0$. Thus $(\bar{R}(e_1, e_2).\bar{R})(e_3, e_1, e_2) = L_{\bar{R}}[((e_1, e_2).\bar{R})(e_3, e_1, e_2)]$ for any function $= L_{\bar{R}} \in C^\infty(M)$.

Similarly, any combination of e_1, e_2 and e_3 we can show (60). Hence M is a pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection.

References

- [1] Samir Abou Akl, On partially pseudosymmetric contact metric three-manifold, *Damascus University Journal for Basic Science*, Vol.24, No 2(2008), pp 17-28.

- [2] F.Defever, R.Deszcz and L.Verstraelen, On pseudosymmetric para-Kähler manifolds, *Colloquium Mathematicum*, Vol. 74, No. 2(1997), pp. 153-160.
- [3] K.Arslan, C.Murathan, C.Ozgur and A.Yildizi, Pseudosymmetric contact metric manifolds in the sense of M.C. Chaki, *Proc. Estonian Acad. Sci. Phys. Math.*, 2001, 50, 3, 124-132.
- [4] R.Deszcz, On pseudo-symmetric spaces, *Bull. Soc. Math. Belg.*, Ser. A, 44(1992), 1-34.
- [5] M.Belkhefha, R.Deszcz and L.Verstraelen, Symmetric properties of Sasakian space forms, *Soochow Journal of Mathematics*, Vol 31, No 4, pp.611-616, Oct., 2005.
- [6] D.G.Prakashs, C.S.Bagewadi and N.S.Basavarajappa, On pseudosymmetric Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds, *IJPAM*, Vol. 48, No.1, 2008, 57-65.
- [7] A.Yildiz, M.Turan and B.F.Acet, On three dimensional Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifolds, *Bulletin of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, Vol. 1, Issue 3(2009), pp. 90-98.
- [8] M.C.Chaki and B.Chaki, On pseudo symmetric manifolds admitting a type of semisymmetric connection, *Soochow Journal of Mathematics*, vol. 13, No. 1, June 1987, 1-7.
- [9] R.Deszcz, F.Defever, L.Verstraelen and L.Vraneken, On pseudosymmetric spacetimes, *J. Math. Phys.*, 35(1994), 5908-5921.
- [10] C.Oğür, On Kenmotsu manifolds satisfying certain pseudosymmetric conditions, *World Applied Science Journal*, 1 (2); 144-149, 2006.
- [11] R.Deszcz, On Ricci-pseudosymmetric warped products, *Demonstratio Math.*, 22(1989), 1053-1065.